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Computational Aeroacoustic Investigation of Co-rotating rotors for Urban Air Mobility

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Abstract

Aerodynamic performance and acoustic far-field of a small-scale, co-axial co-rotating rotor in hover are investigated by means of Lattice-Boltzmann Very-Large-Eddy simulations. The study focuses on the effect of the phase angle between the two co-rotating propellers. Co-rotating rotors are further compared with an isolated rotor. The study demonstrates that increasing the azimuthal separation between the two co-rotating rotors, is beneficial for thrust production and noise reduction in the propeller plane because of destructive interference.

Nomenclature

A	=	rotor disc area, m ²	N_b	=	number of rotor blades
A_b	=	rotor blade area, m ²	r	=	radial location, m
A_d	=	actuator disc diameter, m	R	=	rotor radius, m
c	=	blade chord, m	Re_{75}	=	Reynolds number at 75% radial location
c_{75}	=	blade chord at 75% radial location, m	T	=	rotor thrust force, N
C_T	=	rotor thrust coefficient	V_w	=	flow velocity in the propeller wake, m/sec
C_{Tr}	=	radial thrust coefficient distribution	V_∞	=	freestream velocity, m/sec
C_T/σ	=	blade loading coefficient	V_θ	=	tangential velocity induced by a vortex, m/sec
D	=	rotor diameter, m	Δz	=	axial separation, m
Δf	=	frequency resolution, Hz	$\Delta\phi$	=	azimuthal separation, deg
M_t	=	blade tip Mach number	ρ	=	density of air, kg/m ³
n	=	rotational speed, rotations per second (rps)	σ	=	rotor solidity
N	=	total number of voxels in a resolution region			

1 Introduction

In the past few years, Urban Air Mobility (UAM) has seen a rapid development. It involves developing fully electric Personal Air Vehicles (PAV) for rapid mobility of people. Since these air vehicles operate in an urban environment, public acceptance plays a key role; therefore, amongst other factors, it is essential to lower their noise signature, for given aerodynamic performances. The dominant aerodynamic noise source in these air vehicles is the propulsion system that is based on isolated or distributed propellers.

In order to meet the noise and aerodynamic requirements, keeping into account installation constraints, unconventional configurations must be explored such as co-axial co-rotating rotors [23]. They are characterized by two

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rotors, connected to the same shaft, rotating in the same direction. The distance between the two rotors can vary as well as the azimuthal angle between the propeller blades (named also phase angle). This configuration has gained scientific interest in the last years due to its potential as a low-noise design for hover and forward flight conditions.

The idea of a stacked co-rotating rotor was used for the first time in the automotive industry in 1909 by Mackness, who utilized non uniform rotor blade spacing to enhance cooling fan performance. The first aerospace applications were seen in tail rotors of Apache AH-64D helicopters in the 1970s which comprised of non-orthogonal scissor-shaped stacked rotors. These configurations reduce the noise tonal component at the first Blade Passing Frequency (BPF) as shown by Gardner [12] and Mellin and Sovran [16]. This was further proven by Dobrzynski [9] who showed that due to destructive interference between the pressure signals of azimuthally shifted stacked rotor blades, there is 4 dB(A) drop in sound intensity in the rotor plane.

In 1974, Landgrebe and Bellinger [13] performed experiments with a small scale 2×3 -bladed co-rotating rotor in hover and showed that, with azimuthal separations of 30° and 45° , improvements in performance when compared to a co-planar configuration can be obtained. Aerodynamic performances further increase with increasing axial separations between the two rotors. Rorke [18], using a similar full scale rotor, by testing 4 different azimuthal separation angles of 25.2° , 34.4° , 43.6° and 62.1° , measured 4 dB noise reduction at the first BPF for 43.6° configuration and 6.1% thrust increase for 34.4° configuration. The latter was achieved by setting a differential collective pitch between the two rotors, with the upper rotor pitch angle being 1° higher than the lower one. Tinney [23] performed experiments on a 2×2 -bladed co-rotating rotor and showed a 4.5 dB decrease in overall noise value when the upper rotor led the lower rotor by 102° , compared to the case when this azimuthal separation was just 12° , which shows a higher destructive interference in the former.

Co-rotating rotors also show benefits when compared to contra-rotating ones. A comparison between 2×3 -bladed co-rotating and contra-rotating rotor systems by Bhagwat [2] showed that the former achieve a 4% gain in Figure of Merit (FOM) values when the upper rotor led the lower rotor by 15° . A similar comparison by Uehara and Sirohi [24] showed a 4% decrease in induced power coefficient with the value of the azimuthal separation being 10° .

From a fundamental perspective, Tinney and Valdez [23] proposed that noise reduction is caused by destructive interference between acoustic waves. In order to prove this statement and further explore the complex aerodynamic interaction between the two rotors, high-fidelity numerical simulations are carried out on the same geometry used in Tinney's experiments. Lattice-Boltzmann Very-Large-Eddy Simulations (LB-VLES) are carried out with the commercial software 3DS Simulia PowerFLOW.

2 Computational Methodology and Setup

2.1 LBM Methodology

The LB method is used to compute the flow field because it was shown to be accurate and efficient for similar applications. The commercial software 3DS Simulia PowerFLOW 6-2019 is used. The software solves the discrete LB equation for a finite number of directions. For a detailed description of the method, the reader can refer to Succi [21] and Shan et al. [20], while to Chen and Doolen [7] for a review. The LB method determines the macroscopic flow variables starting from the mesoscopic kinetic equation, i.e. the LB equation. The discretization used for this particular application consists of 19 discrete velocities in three dimensions (D3Q19), involving a third-order truncation of the Chapman-Enskog expansion [5]. The distribution of particles is solved by means of the LB equation on a Cartesian mesh, known as a lattice. An explicit time integration and a collision model are used. For the collision term, the formulation based on a unique Galilean invariant [6] is used. The equilibrium distribution of Maxwell-Boltzmann is adopted [5].

A Very Large Eddy Simulation (VLES) model is implemented to take into account the effect of the sub-grid unresolved scales of turbulence. Following Yakhot and Orszag [27], a two-equations $k - \epsilon$ Renormalization Group is used to compute a turbulent relaxation time that is added to the viscous relaxation time. To reduce the computational cost, a pressure-gradient-extended wall-model is used to approximate the no-slip boundary condition on solid walls [22, 26]. The model is based on the extension of the generalized law-of-the-wall model [14] to take into account the effect of pressure gradient. These equations are iteratively solved from the first cell close to the wall in order to specify the boundary conditions of the turbulence model. For this purpose, a slip algorithm [7], obtained as generalization of a bounce-back and specular reflection process, is used.

The LB scheme is inherently unsteady and compressible with the low dissipation and dispersion properties, which allows it to resolve the sound pressure field directly up to a cutoff frequency corresponding to approximately 15 voxels per acoustic wavelength. Due to this requirement, however, it is often more feasible to employ an

acoustics analogy for obtaining far-field noise. In this study, far-field noise is computed using the Ffowcs Williams and Hawkins [11] (FW-H) analogy. In particular, the formulation 1A of Farassat and Succi [10] extended to a convective wave equation is used in this study [3]. The formulation has been implemented in the time domain using a source-time dominant algorithm [4]. Pressure fluctuations are recorded on three permeable surfaces. This approach considers a distribution of acoustic dipoles on the aerofoil surface [8], while other nonlinear contributions (e.g., turbulent aerofoil wake) are neglected.

2.2 Computational setup

A fixed-pitch 2×2-bladed co-rotating co-axial APC 18×5.5 MR propeller is used. The geometrical description of each propeller has been reported by Tinney and Valdez [23]. Figure 1 shows the geometry in two different views together with key parameters. The upper rotor is in light blue, while the lower rotor is grey; n is the angular velocity (rotations per second) with the arrow representing the orientation of rotation, $\Delta\phi$ is the azimuthal separation between blades of the top and bottom rotor; and Δz is axial separation, i.e. the distance between the upper and lower rotor.

For this study, two configurations with two different azimuthal separations are investigated. They were selected from the large database reported by Tinney and Valdez [23]. The parameters that describe the two configurations are summarized in table 1. For both configurations, the blade-tip Mach number and chord-based Reynolds number based on the chord length at 75% of the radius $c_{75}=3.02$ cm are $M_t = 0.21$ and $Re_{75} = 1.1 \times 10^5$ respectively. They are obtained using the dynamic viscosity of air equal to 1.81×10^{-5} kg/(m s) at standard pressure and temperature, and density of 1.225 kg/m³. In addition, a single 2-bladed APC 18×5.5 MR propeller is simulated at the same condition as reference case, which will be referenced as 'isolated rotor' in the following pages.

To prevent flow separation and ensure a fully turbulent boundary layer on the blade, a zig-zag trip is used on both the pressure and suction sides of the blades at 15% of the local chord. The trip is located from 15% to 95% of the blade radius and the trip thickness is kept lower than the local boundary layer thickness. A similar approach is used in a similar study by Nardari et al. [17].

Figure 1: Co-rotating rotor geometry; upper rotor (light blue) and lower rotor (grey) and symbolic locations of probes used by Tinney [23]. Zig-zag trips can also be seen in the top view.

Configuration	Δz	$\Delta\phi$	n
1	1.1in (2.79cm)	84°	50 rps
2	1.1in (2.79cm)	12°	50 rps

Table 1: Co-rotating rotor configurations; C1 and C2 in short

A cubic computational domain measuring $180D$ on each side, with the rotor at the center, is used. The boundary

conditions on each side of the computational domain are reported in figure 2. The static pressure is set at 101.325 kPa and the freestream velocity is set at 0.05 m/sec, thus mimicking hover conditions.

Figure 2: Schematic of the simulation domain sliced along the center of rotor hub

The simulation domain is discretized with a Cartesian grid. The highest resolution regions are placed near the blade surface while the lowest resolution regions are away from the blade surface and the rotor. Additional mesh refinement is done around the zig-zag trips and blade tips, due to their significance in capturing accurate flow physics in a rotor flow field. The mesh size, referenced as "voxel" size here from, are chosen such that $y^+ = 54.6$ on the blade surface, which reduces to $y^+ = 18.2$ on the zig-zag trip. The resulting number of fine equivalent voxels for the current study is 75 million.

The simulation time is 0.16 sec, which corresponds to a total of 8 rotor rotations. After 2 transient rotations, results are sampled for 6 rotations. The flow field from a lower resolution simulation is used to seed the finer one.

The far field aeroacoustic analysis is performed using the permeable formulation of the Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings [11] acoustic analogy. A total of 3 spherical surfaces surrounding the rotor flow field are used as permeable FWH surfaces, as shown in figure 2. In order to remove spurious noise caused by the hydrodynamic fluctuations in the wake of the propeller, data are sampled on the 3 permeable surfaces and far-field noise results are averaged.

To capture an acoustic wave accurately, a criteria for minimum of 10 points per wavelength is chosen [19]. This resulted in a maximum frequency cutoff of 9300 Hz or 93 times the BPF. Far field analysis is performed at the same locations used by Tinney and Valdez [23] as shown in figure 1 (c). Pressure spectra are then calculated using a Hanning window of 50% overlap and a frequency resolution (Δf) of 10 Hz.

3 Results

3.1 Validation

In order to validate the computational setup, the grid convergence study and comparison with the experiments of Tinney and Valdez [23] are carried out. Configuration 1 is used for the grid convergence study since strong fluid dynamic interaction is expected between the two rotors given higher value of thrust reported by Tinney and Valdez [23]. Four grids, obtained by doubling the resolution of each variable resolution region, are investigated. The number of fine equivalent voxels for each grid are reported in table 2.

The thrust C_T and torque C_Q coefficients are used as integral parameters to assess convergence. They are

defined as

$$C_T = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D^4}, \quad (1)$$

$$C_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho n^2 D^5}, \quad (2)$$

where, T and Q are the rotor thrust and torque in N, respectively, ρ is fluid (air) density in kg/m^3 , n is rotor rotational speed in Hz and D is rotor diameter in m.

Figure 3 shows the aerodynamic results of the grid convergence study. Figure 3 (a) shows the total thrust and torque as a function of the number of fine equivalent voxels, while figure 3 (b) the thrust coefficient distribution (C_{Tr}) along the radial direction. The results show that all the investigated parameters converge for the 'Medium' resolution configuration.

Resolution	Fine equivalent voxels (millions)
Very Coarse (Vcoarse)	14
Coarse	38
Medium	75
Fine	153

Table 2: Number of fine equivalent voxels for each resolution

Figure 3: Grid convergence study for aerodynamic parameters for configuration 1

The effect of the grid on far-field noise is also analyzed. Figure 4 shows far-field noise results at probe 2 and probe 8 for three grid resolutions. Both probes show that almost no difference is present in terms of far-field noise between the coarse and medium grid. Based on the previous observations, the 'Medium' grid resolution is selected for the rest of the study.

The thrust coefficient C_T for both configurations is compared against the measurements carried out by Tinney and Valdez [23] in table 3. A difference of 12.3% with respect to the experiments is observed for both configurations. However, the relative variation between the two configurations is similar, thus suggesting that relative comparison will still provide insights on the interaction between the two rotors. The discrepancy between the experiments and the numerical simulations may be caused by multiple factors. Amongst them it is important to mention that, in the experiments, the thrust was measured during slow startup and shutdown cycles of the electric

Figure 4: Grid convergence study for aeroacoustic parameters of configuration 1

	PowerFLOW	Experiment	Relative error over experiment
Configuration 1	0.091	0.104	12.34%
Configuration 2	0.087	0.099	12.29%

Table 3: Comparison of C_T values for PowerFLOW and experiments

motor to avoid heating issues, whereas in case of present work, the thrust is calculated when the steady-state is achieved.

The co-axial co-rotating configurations are further compared with the single isolated rotor configuration. In order to have a fair comparison between the two configurations, the blade-loading coefficient, which provides a correction for rotor solidity, is used:

$$C_T/\sigma = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D^4 \sigma}. \quad (3)$$

In the equation, $\sigma = A_b/A = N_b c_{75}/\pi R$ is the rotor solidity, where A_b is rotor blade area, A is rotor disc area, N_b is number of rotor blades and R is rotor radius.

Table 4 shows that for configuration 1 and 2, C_T/σ is reduced by 26% and 29% with respect to the isolated 2-bladed rotor, respectively. These results agree with the findings of Tinney and Valdez [23] who measured a decrease of about 30% for a similar comparison. Similarly, Uehara and Sirohi [24] measured a decrease of 20% of C_T/σ by comparing an isolated and a co-rotating rotor at constant power.

	Isolated rotor	Configuration 1	Configuration 2
Value	0.731	0.542	0.519

Table 4: Comparison of C_T/σ values obtained from PowerFLOW for different configurations

3.2 Aerodynamics

The C_T and C_Q for the two configurations provide integral information on the performances of the co-axial co-rotating configurations. In order to dig into the physics of interaction between the two rotors and the differences between the two configurations, a more detailed analysis is carried out.

First, the sectional thrust coefficient C_{Tr} is shown in figure 5. The two co-axial co-rotating configurations are compared with the isolated one. The figure shows that coupling two rotors has a strong effect on both the amplitude and radial distribution of C_{Tr} . More in details, the local maximum at $r/R = 0.9$ present for the isolated rotors is smoothed for the upper blades, independently of the configurations, instead it is present for the lower blade. By changing the azimuthal angle between the blades of the upper and lower rotor it can be seen that for $\Delta\phi = 84^\circ$, both upper and lower blades show a reduction of the C_{Tr} with respect to the isolated blade. The upper blade generates more thrust than the lower one up to $r/R = 0.9$, while for $0.9 < r/R < 1$ the thrust from the lower blade is higher. This is because the upper rotor is acting in a clean freestream flow while the lower rotor acts in a disturbed flow by the upper rotor as shown by the vorticity contour plot in figure 6. By decreasing $\Delta\phi$, the

aerodynamic interaction between the upper and lower rotor is stronger and the upper blade shows larger amplitude of the sectional C_{Tr} with respect to the isolated configuration up to $r/R = 0.8$, but with a stronger reduction of the sectional C_{Tr} for the lower blade; this is quantified and summarized in table 5.

Figure 5: Sectional C_{Tr} distribution in the radial direction for all configurations

	Isolated rotor	Configuration 1		Configuration 2	
		Upper rotor	Lower rotor	Upper rotor	Lower rotor
C_T	0.061	0.054	0.037	0.067	0.020

Table 5: Comparison of C_T values for individual rotors of each configuration with the isolated rotor

The presented results are in agreement with the one presented by Bain and Hennes [1], Bhagwat [2], Landgrebe and Bellinger [13], Rorke [18] and Whiteside et al. [25]. Based on the previous observations, it is possible to conclude that two major flow phenomena must be investigated in order to fully describe the aerodynamic interaction:

- Potential flow interaction;
- Blade wake or vortex interaction.

As potential interaction it is meant the effect on the streamtube [15] formed around each of the rotor disk because of the presence of two rotors. A co-axial co-rotating rotor setup can be seen as a superposition of two streamtubes of the upper and lower rotor. This interaction is investigated by showing the radial distribution of axial velocity at the rotor plane and AoA perceived by the rotor in figure 7. The AoA is estimated by combining the time-averaged velocity components (axial and tangential) sampled at the rotating plane of the blade to calculate the inflow angle and subtracting it from the blade twist angle. It is worth mentioning that the total velocity perceived by the rotor blade is obtained through vectoral sum with the tangential velocity.

The figure 7 shows that at the rotor plane of the lower rotor there is an increase of the axial velocity with respect to the isolated configuration, while for the upper rotor the axial velocity can be higher or lower than the isolated case depending on the configuration. The fact that the lower rotor sees a higher axial velocity is due to the fact that is located in the wake of the upper rotor, which contracts. This also explains why there is a sharp decrease of the velocity at $r/R > 0.8$. At this radial location the shear layer at the edge of the wake is formed. Similarly, the upper rotor experiences a variation of the velocity with respect to the isolated configuration depending on the loading of the lower one. The increase in axial velocity reflects in the decrease of AoA values and subsequently the sectional C_{Tr} values in figure 5.

Another important aspect to consider, particularly when reducing the azimuthal distance between the rotors, is the potential interaction between the two rotor blades, with the one of the lower rotor acting as a flap of the upper one. This may explain why the axial velocity decreases for the upper blade of 12° case, as compared to 84° case.

Figure 6: Vorticity contour plots showing interaction of tip and trailing edge vortices with rotor blades

Following to the momentum theory [15], as upper rotor thrust increases, velocity in its wake also increases which increases the axial velocity values induced for the lower blade, for the 84° configuration as compared to 12° case. This decreases the AoA values for the lower blade and also the sectional C_{Tr} values. Since this flap effect is due to the close proximity of both the rotor blades, it is important only in cases of lower azimuthal separations.

On the top of the potential flow interaction between the two rotors, it is important to account for blade wake/tip-vortex interaction, with the latter affecting the thrust distribution towards the tip ($0.8 < r/R < 1$).

Figure 8 (a) shows the trajectories of the tip vortices while figure 8 (b) the travel speed of each vortex in the downstream direction; vortex age ($^\circ$) for each vortex represents the angle the rotor has already rotated after the tip vortex is formed. The upper rotor tip vortex shows a trajectory very similar to the one of the isolated configuration, while the one from the lower rotor contracts less.

The major effect of the interaction between the two rotors is that the velocity of propagation of the tip vortices is different with respect to the isolated case. This is shown by the different slopes of the curves in the figure and it has an effect on the interaction between the lower rotor and the blade which in turns affects the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic performances of the rotor. It is observed that for this reason, the lower rotor shape shall be designed accounting for such interaction in order to improve aerodynamic performances.

Figure 7: Sectional distribution of aerodynamic parameters in the radial direction for all configurations

Figure 8: Tip vortex trajectory locations in the rotor flowfield

3.3 Aeroacoustics

Noise spectra are plotted at two different probe locations and compared with the experimental results from Tinney and Valdez [23] in figure 9. The results show the dominance of the tonal noise component at the first and second BPF (i.e., 100 and 200 Hz respectively), independently of the configuration, while at higher frequencies broadband noise dominates. When comparing with experimental results, there is a difference of about 3 dB for the first BPF, which can be attributed to the difference in thrust between experiments and numerical simulations described above. At higher frequencies, the discrepancies between the experiments and simulations are higher; they are attributed to background noise of the facility. Furthermore, high harmonics tones are present in the experiments and not in the

numerical simulations. They resemble the ones observed by Nardari et al. [17], and they were attributed to flow re-circulation within the anechoic chamber.

Figure 9: Noise spectra comparison between configuration 1 and 2 for both PowerFLOW and experiment

When comparing the two co-rotating configurations, configuration 2 exhibits a higher value of the tonal noise at the first BPF with respect to configuration 1, i.e. 16.7 dB/Hz higher noise for probe 2 and 16 dB/Hz for probe 8. This is due to destructive interference between the acoustic wave radiated by the upper and lower rotors, as mentioned by Tinney and Valdez [23]. This is clearly shown in figure 10 where the time-variation of the acoustic pressure at the two probes is plotted for one full rotor rotation (0.02 sec). It is evident that for configuration 1, the acoustic waves are more out of phase with respect to the case of configuration 2, thus justifying the different tonal noise components.

This is further shown in figure 11 where the Overall SPL (OASPL), in the frequency range 90-4000 Hz, is plotted at all probes. The figure highlights the effect on directivity of the azimuthal angle; configuration 2 shows a directivity plot which is similar to the isolated rotor case, while configuration 1 clearly shows a strong reduction at the rotor plane (about 14 dB) and similar values as configuration 2 at more downstream locations.

Figure 10: Time variation of the acoustic pressure sampled at probe 2 and probe 8

Figure 11 also shows the OASPL values for two different 2-bladed rotors (dotted lines), each of them having thrust values equal to the two co-rotating rotor configurations. This was done by increasing the collective pitch angle of blades of the isolated rotor by 5° for comparison with configuration 1 and 4.5° for comparison with configuration 2. In case of configuration 1, co-rotating rotor produces less noise than the corresponding 2-bladed rotor for most of the probe locations, except in case of out-of-plane probes where values are very close or, in some cases, higher for the co-rotating rotor. For configuration 2, noise values are higher at all probes for the co-rotating than the corresponding 2-bladed rotor. This underlines the role of higher azimuthal separation, especially for locations near the rotating plane, to achieve lower noise values when seeking to replace a 2-bladed rotor with a co-rotating rotor producing the same thrust.

Figure 11: OASPL values calculated at all probes for configuration 1 and configuration 2. Dotted lines represent OASPL values for 2-bladed rotor with the same thrust of the co-rotating configuration.

4 Conclusions

An aerodynamic and aeroacoustic investigation was conducted on a 2×2 -bladed co-rotating rotor formed by two identical 2-bladed APC 18×5.5 MR propeller stacked on top of each other. By varying the azimuthal separation between the upper and lower rotor blades while keeping all other variables the same, two separate configurations were simulated and compared. To understand the behaviour of upper and lower rotor separately, each of them was compared to the results of a 2-bladed isolated rotor operating at the same flow conditions. The mesh convergence behaviour was studied and results were also validated with experimental data for the same set of co-rotating rotors.

The rotor with higher azimuthal separation showed an increased thrust value than compared to the rotor with lower azimuthal separation. The aerodynamic behaviour of the co-rotating system is affected by: a potential non-viscous effect because of the mutual interaction of streamtubes of the two rotors; and rotor-wake/rotor-tip vortex interaction. It is further noticed that for the configuration with lower azimuthal separation the lower blade acts as a flap for the upper rotor.

Noise was calculated by performing a far-field analysis using Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkings (FWH) methodology. It is found that, for a given thrust, the acoustic benefit of the co-rotating configuration is present only for a larger azimuthal angle because of the destructive interference between the acoustic waves.

The study provides various points where further investigations can be performed. As mentioned by Tinney and Valdez [23] for a small scale rotor, tip loss and Reynolds number effects need to be taken into account. It is hypothesized that best aerodynamic and aeroacoustic performances can be obtained using upper and lower rotors with different pitch angles. These studies can be complemented with studies on increased rotational speed of the co-rotating rotor and the corresponding change in noise values, and comparison with a 4-bladed co-planar rotor to have a fair comparison with 2×2 -bladed co-rotating rotor.

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